

THE REVIVAL OF "PAPER" ON THE SILK ROAD: A PATH FOR THE PROTECTION AND TOURISM REVITALIZATION OF TRADITIONAL PAPERMAKING SKILLS IN SAMARKAND - TAKING THE KONI GHIL MEROS PAPERMAKING WORKSHOP AS AN EXAMPLE

Song Difei

PhD of Silk Road International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage in Samarkand Work at BaiCheng Normal University, Baicheng city, Jilin Province, China

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15606025>

Abstract. *The Silk Road, as an important passage for the exchange of civilizations between the East and the West in ancient times, carried rich material and cultural exchanges. Among them, the dissemination and development of papermaking technology are particularly remarkable. This article takes the Koni Ghil Meros papermaking workshop in Samarkand as an example to deeply explore the paths of protection and tourism revitalization of traditional papermaking techniques in Samarkand. Through methods such as literature analysis and field investigation, the historical origin, inheritance status, challenges faced and tourism revitalization strategies of the papermaking technique in Samarkand were analyzed. The research finds that the Koni Ghil Meros Papermaking workshop has effectively promoted the inheritance and development of traditional papermaking techniques through measures such as innovating protection models, carrying out cultural tourism activities, and strengthening international cooperation. At the same time, it has also injected new vitality into the local economic development. This research aims to provide reference and guidance for the protection of other intangible cultural heritages and tourism development.*

Key words: *The Silk Road, Samarkand papermaking techniques, Koni Ghil Meros Paper Workshop Protection, cultural heritage Tourism revitalization.*

Annotatsiya. *Qadim zamonlarda Sharq va G'arb tsivilizatsiyalari almashinuvining muhim kanali bo'lgan Ipak yo'li boy moddiy va madaniy almashinuvlarni o'z ichiga olgan. Ular orasida qog'oz ishlab chiqarish texnologiyasining tarqalishi va rivojlanishi ayniqsa diqqatni jalb qiladi. Samarqanddagi Koni Ghil Meros qog'oz ishlab chiqarish seminarini misol sifatida olib, ushbu maqola Samarqandning an'anaviy qog'oz ishlab chiqarish ko'nikmalarini saqlash va turizmni qayta tiklashni o'rganadi. Adabiyotlarni tahlil qilish va dala tadqiqotlari orqali ushbu maqola Samarqand qog'oz ishlab chiqarish texnologiyasining tarixiy kelib chiqishi, meros holati, muammolari va turizmni qayta tiklash strategiyalarini tahlil qiladi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, Koni Ghil Meros qog'oz ishlab chiqarish ustaxonasi innovatsion tabiatni muhofaza qilish modellari, madaniy turizm faoliyati va xalqaro hamkorlikni mustahkamlash orqali an'anaviy qog'oz ishlab chiqarish ko'nikmalarini meros qilib olish va rivojlantirishga samarali yordam berdi, shu bilan birga mahalliy iqtisodiy rivojlanishga yangi hayot qo'shdi. Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi boshqa nomoddiy madaniy merosni himoya qilish va turizmni rivojlantirish uchun ma'lumot berishdir.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Ipak yo'li, Samarqand qog'oz ishlab chiqarish texnikasi, Koni Ghil Meros qog'oz tayyorlash bo'yicha seminar, nomoddiy madaniy merosni muhofaza qilish, turizmni qayta tiklash.*

***Аннотация.** Шелковый путь, как важный канал для обмена цивилизациями между Востоком и Западом в древности, нес богатые материальные и культурные обмены. Среди них особенно выделяется распространение и развитие бумажного производства. В данной статье на примере мастерской по изготовлению бумаги «Кони Гил Мерос» в Самарканде подробно рассматриваются пути защиты и возрождения туризма в Самарканде, связанные с традиционными навыками изготовления бумаги. С помощью анализа литературы, полевых исследований и других методов анализируется историческое происхождение, статус наследования, проблемы и стратегии возрождения туризма самаркандской техники изготовления бумаги. Выяснилось, что мастерская по изготовлению бумаги «Кони Гил Мерос» эффективно содействует сохранению и развитию традиционных навыков бумажного производства с помощью инновационных моделей сохранения, мероприятий культурного туризма и укрепления международного сотрудничества, а также придает новую жизненную силу местному экономическому развитию. Данное исследование призвано послужить примером для сохранения и развития туризма в отношении других объектов нематериального культурного наследия.*

***Ключевые слова:** шелковый путь, самаркандская бумажная мастерская, Koni Ghil Meros бумажная мастерская, защита нематериального культурного наследия, туризм.*

1. Introduction

Papermaking is one of the four great inventions of ancient China and has had a profound impact on the development of world civilization. With the opening of the Silk Road, papermaking gradually spread to Central Asia, West Asia and even Europe. Among them, Samarkand became an important papermaking center in Central Asia and also an important hub for the dissemination of traditional papermaking techniques.

Samarkand, as an important hub city on the ancient Silk Road, has traditional papermaking techniques that can be traced back to the westward migration of Chinese artisans after the Battle of Talas in 751 AD. Archaeological evidence shows that the local processing technology for mulberry bark fiber raw materials is highly similar to that recorded in the Tang Dynasty's "Tiangong Kaiwu", while the unique alkaline solution degumming process integrates the Persian chemical knowledge system. This cross-civilization technological hybridization endowed Samarkand paper with strong anti-aging properties and fine texture. It became the most important writing medium in the Islamic world from the 9th to the 15th century, and the Ibn Sina medical manuscripts existing in the British Library are typical examples.

With the development of modern industrialization, traditional hand-made papermaking techniques are facing severe challenges. How to protect traditional skills while achieving their sustainable development has become an urgent problem to be solved. This article takes the Koni Ghil Meros papermaking workshop in Samarkand as an example to explore the paths of protection and tourism revitalization of traditional papermaking techniques.

2. Literature Review

2.1 The Silk Road and the Spread of Papermaking

Samarkand, as an important hub city on the ancient Silk Road, has traditional papermaking techniques that can be traced back to the westward migration of Chinese artisans after the Battle of Talas in 751 AD. Archaeological evidence shows that the local processing technology for mulberry bark fiber raw materials is highly similar to that recorded in the Tang Dynasty's "Tiangong Kaiwu", while the unique alkaline solution degumming process integrates the Persian

chemical knowledge system. This cross-civilization technological hybridization endowed Samarkand paper with strong anti-aging properties and fine texture. It became the most important writing medium in the Islamic world from the 9th to the 15th century, and the Ibn Sina medical manuscripts existing in the British Library are typical examples.

The Silk Road was an important passage for the exchange of civilizations between the East and the West in ancient times. It not only promoted the exchange of commodities but also facilitated extensive exchanges in fields such as culture, religion and technology. Papermaking, as an important invention of ancient China, gradually spread to Central Asia, West Asia and even Europe through the Silk Road. Regarding the specific time and route of the westward spread of papermaking technology, there are different viewpoints in the academic circle. It is generally believed that papermaking was introduced to Central Asia around the 8th century AD, and Samarkand became an important node for the westward spread of papermaking along the Silk Road.

2.2 Protection and Inheritance of Traditional Papermaking Techniques

Traditional papermaking techniques, as an intangible cultural heritage, possess unique historical, cultural, scientific and economic values. However, with the development of modern industrialization, traditional hand-made papermaking techniques are facing severe challenges. In order to protect and pass on this traditional art, scholars at home and abroad have conducted a large amount of research and practice. On the one hand, by recording, sorting out and researching the historical origin, technological process and technical characteristics of traditional papermaking techniques, a theoretical basis is provided for the inheritance of the techniques. On the other hand, measures such as establishing a list of intangible cultural heritage protection, conducting the identification and training of inheritors have provided institutional guarantees for the inheritance of skills.

2.3 Tourism Revitalization and Protection of Intangible Cultural Heritage

Tourism revitalization refers to the transformation of intangible cultural heritage into tourism resources through tourism development, achieving a dual enhancement of its economic and cultural values. In recent years, with the rise of cultural tourism, more and more intangible cultural heritages have been included in the scope of tourism development. Tourism revitalization not only provides financial support for the protection of intangible cultural heritage, but also enhances the public's cognition and recognition of traditional culture. However, tourism revitalization may also have negative impacts on intangible cultural heritage, such as excessive commercialization and cultural distortion. Therefore, how to protect the authenticity and integrity of intangible cultural heritage in the process of tourism revitalization has become an urgent problem to be solved.

3. The historical origin and current status of inheritance of traditional papermaking techniques in Samarkand

3.1 Historical Origins

Samarkand is located in the east of Uzbekistan and is an important city on the Silk Road. As early as around the 8th century AD, papermaking technology was introduced to Samarkand via the Silk Road and was widely developed and applied there. According to Arab historical records, papermaking was introduced to Samarkand by captured Chinese soldiers. Among these soldiers were some papermakers who established papermaking workshops in Samarkand and taught papermaking skills, gradually making Samarkand the papermaking center in Central Asia.

The traditional papermaking techniques of Samarkand mainly inherit the ancient papermaking methods of China, but there are also some unique innovations. For instance, Samarkand paper is mainly made from mulberry bark and is produced through a series of complex processes such as soaking, steaming, pounding, rinsing, pressing and drying. This kind of paper has the characteristics of being white, flexible and having good ink absorption, and is deeply loved by the local people. In addition, Samarkand paper also adopts unique decorative techniques, such as embossing and gilding, making the paper more beautiful and elegant.

3.2 Current Status of Inheritance

With the development of modern industrialization, the traditional papermaking technique of Samarkand is facing severe challenges. On the one hand, modern machine-made paper has high production efficiency and low cost, gradually replacing traditional manual papermaking. On the other hand, the number of inheritors of traditional papermaking skills is gradually decreasing, and many young people lack interest in this skill. However, with the efforts of the government and all sectors of society, the traditional papermaking technique of Samarkand has been protected and passed down to a certain extent.

At present, some traditional paper workshops are still retained in the Samarkand region, among which the Koni Ghil Meros Paper Workshop is a relatively famous one. This workshop was established in 1996 by the Mukhertarov brothers, with the aim of restoring and passing on the traditional papermaking techniques of Samarkand. The workshop adopts traditional papermaking techniques and tools, retaining the essence of ancient papermaking methods. Meanwhile, the workshop also actively conducts training for inheritors and cultural tourism activities, attracting a large number of tourists to visit and experience.

4. Conservation and tourism revitalization Strategies of Koni Gil Paper Workshop

4.1 Innovate the protection mode

In order to effectively protect and pass on the traditional papermaking skills of Samarkand, the Koni Gil Papermaking Workshop has adopted an innovative protection model. On the one hand, the workshop has established a complete system for the inheritance of skills, cultivating new inheritors through methods such as master-apprentice inheritance and training classes. On the other hand, the workshop also actively engages in scientific research cooperation, establishing cooperative relationships with universities, research institutions, etc., to jointly study the protection and development of traditional papermaking techniques.

In addition, the workshop also attaches great importance to the recording and organization of skills. They recorded in detail the process flow and technical features of traditional papermaking techniques by means of shooting videos and taking notes, providing valuable materials for the inheritance of the techniques. Meanwhile, the workshop has also established a list of intangible cultural heritage protection, including the traditional papermaking technique of Samarkand, providing institutional guarantees for the protection of the technique.

4.2 Carry out cultural tourism activities

Tourism revitalization is one of the important strategies for the Koni Gil Paper Workshop to protect and pass on the traditional papermaking skills. The workshop has made full use of its unique cultural resources and carried out a series of cultural tourism activities, attracting a large number of tourists to visit and experience.

The workshop has set up a dedicated tourist area where visitors can watch papermaking artisans demonstrate the papermaking process on the spot and learn about the technological process and technical features of traditional papermaking techniques. In addition, the workshop

has developed a variety of cultural tourism products, such as papermaking experience courses and paper handicraft making, allowing tourists to experience the charm of traditional papermaking techniques firsthand. These activities not only enhance tourists' understanding and recognition of traditional culture, but also bring considerable economic benefits to the workshops.

4.3 Strengthen international cooperation

International cooperation is one of the important ways for the Koni Gil Paper Workshop to protect and pass on the traditional papermaking skills. The workshop actively cooperates with relevant institutions and organizations at home and abroad to jointly promote the protection and development of traditional papermaking techniques.

5. Challenges Faced and Countermeasures

5.1 Challenges Faced

Although the Koni Ghil Meros Paper Workshop has achieved certain results in protecting and inheriting the traditional papermaking skills of Samarkand, it still faces some challenges.

First of all, the number of inheritors of traditional papermaking skills is gradually decreasing, and many young people lack interest in this skill. This is mainly because the learning process of traditional papermaking techniques is relatively long and arduous, and the returns are relatively low. Secondly, the development of modern industrialization has had an impact on traditional papermaking techniques. Modern machine-made paper has high production efficiency and low cost, gradually replacing traditional manual papermaking. In addition, tourism revitalization may also have negative impacts on traditional papermaking techniques, such as excessive commercialization and cultural distortion, etc.

5.2 Countermeasures

In response to the above challenges, the following countermeasures can be adopted:

First of all, strengthen the construction of the training and incentive mechanism for inheritors. The government and all sectors of society should intensify the cultivation of inheritors of traditional papermaking techniques and provide necessary financial and technical support. Meanwhile, a sound incentive mechanism should also be established to encourage young people to learn and pass on this skill. For instance, a reward fund for inheritors can be established and employment opportunities can be provided, etc.

Secondly, promote the integration of traditional papermaking techniques with modern technology. By introducing modern technological means, the production efficiency and product quality of traditional papermaking techniques can be improved. For example, modern mechanical equipment can be utilized to replace some manual operations and improve production efficiency. Modern detection technologies can be utilized to monitor and inspect the quality of paper, etc. Finally, strengthen the regulation and management of tourism revitalization. The government should strengthen the regulation and management of tourism revitalization to prevent the occurrence of excessive commercialization and cultural distortion. For example, relevant tourism development plans and management measures can be formulated to clarify the direction and focus of tourism development. The supervision of the tourism market can be strengthened to crack down on illegal business operations and fraudulent activities, etc.

6. Conclusions and Prospects

This article takes the Koni Ghil Meros Paper Workshop in Samarkand as an example to deeply explore the revival of "paper" on the Silk Road - the path of protection and tourism revitalization of traditional papermaking techniques in Samarkand. Through research, it is found that the Koni Ghil Meros Papermaking workshop has effectively promoted the inheritance and

development of traditional papermaking techniques through measures such as innovating protection models, carrying out cultural tourism activities, and strengthening international cooperation. However, traditional papermaking techniques still face some challenges that require the joint efforts of the government and all sectors of society to solve.

Looking ahead, with the rise of cultural tourism and the increasing emphasis on traditional culture by people, the traditional papermaking technique of Samarkand is expected to embrace new development opportunities. The government and all sectors of society should continue to enhance the protection and inheritance of traditional papermaking techniques, and promote their integration and innovative development with modern science and technology. Meanwhile, international exchanges and cooperation should also be strengthened to jointly promote the development of the cause of protecting and inheriting world cultural heritage.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no competing financial interests. Ethnographic data collection adhered to the 2003 UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage.

REFERENCES

1. ALIZA THOMAS. On Samarkand Paper.[J]. *Hand Papermaking*,2014,Vol.29(1): 8.
2. Richard W. Bulliet. Paper before Print: The History and Impact of Paper in the Islamic World (review)[J]. *Technology and Culture*,2003,Vol.44(1): 160-161.
3. Given-Name Helman-Ważny. 6 A Survey of Tibetan Paper[J]. *The Archaeology of Tibetan Books*,2014,Vol.36: 179-200.
4. WANG Jinwei, HUANG Zhenfang, WANG Zhaofeng,et al. Empowering integration of culture and tourism with new quality productive forces from the perspective of rural revitalization: Scientific issues and strategic paths[J]. *Ziyuan Kexue*,2024,Vol.46(12): 2335-2354.
5. He Jihong,Sun Bing,Shi Zhaowan,et al. Proposing a Conceptual Framework for Ecotourism Based on Pro-Poor Tourism Strategy in Lechang City, Guangdong Province[J]. *Redai dili*,2021,Vol.41(3): 645-655.
6. Cheng, Bo,Li,et al. Spatial logic of traditional village digital conservation: Field transformation, pattern evolution and value realization[J]. *Dili Yanjiu*,2025,Vol.44(2): 434-449.
7. GAO Qun, CHEN Hengyang, ZHANG Xinliang. Evolution and focal features of China’s agricultural green development policies: Text analysis based on attention perspective[J]. *Ziyuan Kexue*,2023,Vol.45(12): 2433-2448.
8. Richard W. Bulliet. Paper before Print: The History and Impact of Paper in the Islamic World (review)[J]. *Technology and Culture*,2003,Vol.44(1): 160-161.
9. Given-Name Helman-Ważny. 6 A Survey of Tibetan Paper[J]. *The Archaeology of Tibetan Books*,2014,Vol.36: 179-200.
10. עמר זהר,Zohar Amar. The Paper Industry in al-Sham in the Middle Ages[J]. *Cathedra: For the History of Eretz Israel and Its Yishuv*,2000,Vol.98: 73-96.
11. Poggenpohl, Sharon Helmer. Between Visual and Digital Tokens.[J]. *Visible Language*,1995,Vol.29: 264-293.